

An Electrometric Study on the Quantitative Precipitation of Copper(II) as Tellurate

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Various methods for the determination of copper (II) on micro-scale have been reported in literature. The present investigation is a conductometric study of the reaction between copper nitrate and sodium tellurate and has been taken up with a view to investigate the process as a possible analytical method for the determination of copper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents.—Sodium tellurate (B. D. H.) and cupric nitrate (E. Merck) were dissolved separately in conductivity water. The tellurium content was determined as metallic tellurium¹ and copper as α -benzoin oxime complex ($\text{Cu C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}$).

Apparatus and Procedure.—A Philips conductivity bridge type PR 9500 was used for the electrolytic resistance measurement. The readings were recorded in ohms at an output frequency of 50 cycles/sec. Titrations were carried out in a 100 ml pyrex beaker placed on a magnetic stirrer; a dip cell, type PR 9510, with a cell constant 1.46 was used for the measurements. The dilution correction has also been applied to the observed conductivity values.

Corrected conductivity = $\frac{V+v}{V}$ X observed conductivity, where V is the initial volume of the solution taken in the cell and v is the volume of titrant added. These corrected conductivity values are plotted against the volume in ml of the titrant added. In the preliminary experiments, when the titration was performed in aqueous media, the results obtained were found to be low; however, on the addition of alcohol, the results improved. A number of titrations were therefore carried out at different ethanol concentrations out of which 15% gave the best results.

In the case of direct conductometric titrations, a known volume of cupric nitrate solution with an overall 15% of ethanol by volume was taken in 100 ml. pyrex beaker placed on magnetic stirrer, the cell was properly dipped and the initial resistance recorded. Sodium tellurate solution was added from a microburette in small amounts, the mixture stirred well and the readings recorded after allowing the precipitate to settle down. The end point was obtained by plotting volume of titrant added against the conductance.

1. V. Lehner and A. W. Homberger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 30, 387.

In the reverse titrations sodium tellurate solution containing 15% ethanol was taken in the cell, cupric nitrate added from the micro-burette, the rest of the procedure being as earlier. The results are given in the following table.

TABLE I
Conductometric determination of copper as tellurate

	Volume of titration mixture	=	60 ml.	
	Temperature	=	$25 \pm 0.5^\circ$	
	Ethanol concentration	=	15%	
Concn. of titrate in moles	Amount of Cu^{++} in mg.		Difference in mg	
	Taken	Found		
<i>Direct Titration</i>				
0.869×10^{-4}	0.3316	0.3356	-0.0040	
1.738×10^{-4}	0.6632	0.6640	-0.0008	
2.607×10^{-4}	0.9948	0.9924	+0.0024	
3.651×10^{-4}	1.3930	1.3990	-0.0060	
5.219×10^{-4}	1.9890	1.985	+0.0040	
<i>Reverse Titration</i>				
3.749×10^{-4}	1.428	1.426	+0.002	
5.240×10^{-4}	1.999	1.990	+0.009	
5.614×10^{-4}	2.142	2.155	-0.013	
5.988×10^{-4}	2.284	2.288	-0.004	

DISCUSSION

In the direct titration it was observed that when Na_2TeO_4 was added to $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution, the conductance first decreases, then increases beyond the equivalence point due to the replacement of Cu^{++} ions. In the reverse titration a reverse process occurs. Conductance first increases due obviously to the replacement of less mobile tellurate ion by more mobile nitrate ion and then decreases. The pH measurement of the solution at equivalence point showed that complete precipitation occurs at 5.20 pH.

The function of ethanol (15%) may be to check the dissolution of precipitate and its hydrolysis under cited condition.

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